

GAS PRESSURE INFILTRATION PROCESSING AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ALUMINA AND CARBON FIBERS REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

Aluminium matrix composites plates were elaborated using gas pressure infiltration casting and unidirectional preforms of either alumina or carbon fibers.

Concerning alumina/aluminium composites, the fibers were either pure alumina or alumina-silica fiber. The matrices were either high purity aluminium or Al-Si-Mg alloys with various magnesium contents.

For carbon/aluminium materials, a high modulus carbon fiber and an ultra high modulus graphite fiber were used. On the first one, coatings were tested in order to create a diffusion barrier or a mechanical fuse. The matrices were either pure aluminium or Al-Mg alloys with Mg content up to 10%.

Longitudinal and transverse tensile tests were performed in order to determine the elastic modulus and the ultimate tensile strength.

The study of non-reactive fiber-matrix systems using pure aluminium and alumina fibers allowed to determine the degradation of the reinforcement due to the mechanical damage suffered by the fiber during processing, and the influence of infiltration and solidification defects on the final properties of materials.

The influence of fiber-matrix reactions on mechanical properties of composites was studied on carbon/aluminium. The effects of the precipitation of brittle interfacial carbides in carbone/aluminium composites were evaluated.

Finally the relation between fiber-matrix interface strength and mechanical properties of composites was established for the two fiber/matrix couples.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites reinforced with continuous fibers are considered to be attractive materials as they offer high specific stiffness and specific strength compared to conventional engineering materials.

Strong interest in the aerospace community has driven the development of processing of MMC's either by foil-fiber-foil, or tape casting or PVD coated fiber pressing. These approaches tend to be expensive. Consolidation and the required tooling for component production add

costs far above the material manufacturing price. Thus the problem of cost has stymied the widespread use of these composites (1)(2).

Therefore composites that could be produced by casting offer an attractive alternative for manufacturing net shape parts. Aluminum can be easily and inexpensively cast and also offers a low weight material which, with suitable reinforcement, can offer exceptional mechanical performance.

Alumina, silicon carbide and carbon continuous fibers are different reinforcements suitable for aluminium matrix composites. The systems chosen for evaluation were alumina/aluminium and carbon/aluminium. The second system is very attractive because carbon fibers give the possibility to tailor thermal conductivity and coefficient of thermal expansion while maintaining the lowest density and the highest modulus of any composite system, but the chemical reactivity between carbon fiber and molten aluminium usually limits the tensile strength of the material. Moreover, galvanic corrosion could be an other limitation to the use of carbon/aluminium composites. The alumina/aluminium couple does not present these difficulties but their properties will be limited by the performances of the reinforcement.

Data will be presented showing the salient microstructural features of the composites produced by gas pressure infiltration casting. The results of mechanical testing provide both properties and the fracture behaviour of the samples in longitudinal and transverse tension.

EXPERIMENTAL

Alumina and Carbon fibers were incorporated into aluminum matrices using the gas pressure infiltration casting process. This process has been studied for many years, with a special emphasis at M.I.T. (3)(4)(5)(6)(7). The details of this fabrication process are explained below : The fiber tows were wrapped from the vendor's rolls onto a preform mandril which is a part of the casting mold. The unidirectional fiber preform was pressed in the mold in order to get the expected size and fiber volume fraction. Then the mold was placed in a sealed steel can, and put in a P-CAST 1075 L pressure casting unit as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 . Gas Pressure Infiltration Apparatus

The unit and the mold were evacuated to remove all the air from the preform region, at which time the mold and the metal were then heated under a dynamic vacuum of approximately 1 Torr. After the preform was outgassed and the mold and the melt charges were adjusted to the desired temperatures, the melt was lifted with a hydraulic lifting device to cover the snorkle melt inlet. Nitrogen gas pressure was then applied to force the aluminium to fully infiltrate the preform and the mold, producing a porosity free MMC casting. Temperatures were measured with type K thermocouples embedded in the mold and in a well in the melt crucible. The preform temperature was measured with three thermocouples along the center line of the mold.

Pure aluminium (99.98%) and common casting alloys : Al 7%Si 0.3%Mg (A-356), and Al 7%Si 0.6%Mg (A-357) were used with alumina fibers.

Pure aluminium (99.98%), an experimental alloy Al 4.5%Mg and a commercial alloy Al 10%Mg (520) were used with carbon fibers.

The properties of the fibers used in this study are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 . Fiber properties from suppliers' data sheets

Fiber designation	Composition (wt%)	Filament diameter (μm)	Filament count per tow	Density	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Producer
Almax	99% Al ₂ O ₃ α	10	1 000	3.6	1 800	330	MITSUI
Altex	85% Al ₂ O ₃ 15% SiO ₂	10 - 15	1 000	3.3	1 800	210	SUMITOMO
M 40 J	99.9% C	5	6 000	1.77	4 412	377	TORAY
M 40 B	99.9% C	6.5	3 000	1.81	2 744	392	TORAY
FT 700	99.9% C	10	3 000	2.16	3 300	700	TONEN

For carbon/aluminium materials, high modulus carbon fibers M40B and M40J (PAN precursor) and an ultra high modulus graphite fiber (pitch precursor) were used. On M40B, coatings were tested in order to create a mechanical fuse and a diffusion barrier. It has been shown by Rabinovitch et al (8), that pyrolytic carbon gives a weak interface, and an increase of ultimate tensile strength in cast carbon/aluminium composites.

The first coating used was a pyrolytic carbon (Cp) coating, 90 nm thick, produced by Chemical Vapor Deposition. The second coating was the pyrolytic carbon layer presented above, and a silicon carbide layer created by Reactive Chemical Vapor Deposition from Cp and a gaseous precursor. The SiC layer constituted a diffusion barrier in order to limit the reaction between carbon and aluminium.

Aluminium Matrix Composite plates 150 x 80 x 2 mm in size were cast. A minimum of four specimens for each system, 40 mm gauge length, 2 mm thick and 8 mm wide were cut by abrasive water jet and tested in tension in the longitudinal and the transverse directions.

Selected samples were mounted for metallography and polished using conventional techniques. These ones and fractured specimens were examined by scanning electron microscopy.

Fibers for tensile testing were leached from the castings by immersing in a 5% NaOH solution, in order to determine the degradation of tensile strength as a function of processing. The single fibers were glued to a grip-card with a 10 mm gage port and mounted in a tensile testing

machine. After the card port frame was cut, the fiber was loaded to failure. Thirty individual fiber tests were performed for each processing condition investigated. The fiber strengths were analyzed using Weibull statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Due to poor wettability of fibers by liquid aluminium, each fiber-matrix couple required a specific set of processing parameters. The most important processing parameters are :

- infiltration pressure
- preform temperature
- melt temperature.

The solidification time is a derivative from the primary parameters and the geometry of the mold, preform, and mold chilling scheme.

The infiltration parameters and the results obtained on plates cast for the study are presented in Table 2.

The study of non-reactive fiber-matrix systems using pure aluminium and alumina fibers allowed to determine the influence of infiltration and solidification defects on the final properties of materials.

Microscopic analysis revealed that the critical defects are solidification defects due to either an insufficient control of the unidirectionality of solidification, or a too low preform temperature. Longitudinal properties are rather independent of these defects, on the contrary transverse properties are strongly dependent on elaboration conditions. As shown in Figure 2, on transverse tensile tests, the crack goes through weak areas and the rupture surface reveals the infiltration defects. With the alumina/pure aluminium couple, optimized infiltration parameters produce a strong interface and high transverse tensile strength (95 MPa), as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Almax/pure Al : transverse fracture surface showing infiltration defect
UTS = 40 MPa

Figure 3. Almax/pure Al : transverse fracture surface showing strong interface
UTS = 95 MPa

As shown in Table 2, castings A1 and A2, an increase of metal and preform temperatures has an effect on the transverse strength of alumina/aluminium composites due to less defects in the material. The longitudinal tensile strength of those composites were low compared to calculated values using the rule of mixture (ROM) and the tensile strength of the reinforcement. The hypothesis that a degradation of the reinforcement due to damage suffered by the fiber during

processing has occurred, was denounced by Weibull statistic analysis on reinforcement before and after infiltration. The results are presented in Table 3. It shows that UTS of Almax fibers was much lower than the value announced by the producer, and that processing is only responsible for a 22% loss of mechanical properties of fibers.

Table 2. Tensile properties of aluminium matrix composites

Casting N°	Materials			Processing parameters				Tensile test results average / number of tests / standard deviation			
	Fiber designation	Matrix	Fiber volume fraction (%)	Temperature of molten metal (°C)	Temperature of fiber preform (°C)	Infiltration pressure (MPa)	Maximum time of liquid metal preform contact (s)	Longitudinal direction		Transverse direction	
								Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	
A1	Almax	pure Al	45	682	660	9	190	475 / 7 / 78	168 / 6 / 12	67 / 9 / 9	
A2	Almax	pure Al	45	750	680	9	320	474 / 8 / 58	171 / 8 / 15	94 / 4 / 9	
A3	Altex	pure Al	35	680	660	9	180	516 / 5 / 48	109 / 5 / 3	92 / 3 / 7	
A4	Altex	pure Al	46	750	700	9	153	720 / 6 / 43	121 / 2	84 / 2	
A5	Altex	Al 7Si 0.6Mg	35	640	620	9	300	179 / 3 / 28	108 / 3 / 1	136 / 3 / 5	
A6	Altex	Al 7Si 0.3Mg	35	660	640	9	340	214 / 3 / 16	109 / 3 / 2	113 / 3 / 36	
C1	M 40 J	pure Al	50	700	660	8	178	286 / 4 / 53	218 / 4 / 9	46 / 4 / 6	
C2	M 40 J	Al 4.5 Mg	50	670	660	8	293	776 / 6 / 122	-	-	
C3	M 40 J	Al 10 Mg	50	640	620	8	587	885 / 5 / 77	-	-	
C4	M 40 B	Al 4.5 Mg	50	700	680	8	350	350 / 4 / 40	183 / 2	63 / 2	
C5	M 40 B	Al 4.5 Mg	50	670	660	8	252	640 / 5 / 75	-	-	
C6	M 40 B + Cp	Al 4.5 Mg	50	670	660	8	302	1016 / 6 / 96	-	-	
C7	M 40B+Cp+SiC	Al 4.5 Mg	50	670	660	8	293	1073 / 6 / 60	-	-	
C8	FT 700	pure Al	70	750	700	8	171	1147 / 8 / 70	370 / 4 / 16	30 / 1	
C9	FT 700	pure Al	70	700	670	8	156	1257 / 8 / 87	357 / 7 / 15	29 / 1	
C10	FT 700	Al 4.5 Mg	70	670	660	8	247	912 / 8 / 150	365 / 2	12 / 3 / 4	
C11	FT 700	Al 7Si 0.6Mg	75	690	660	8	369	999 / 3 / 41	395 / 1	-	

Table 3. Tensile properties of single fibers

Fiber designation	As received fibers		Leached fibers		
	Tensile strength (MPa)	Weibull's modulus	Casting N°	Tensile strength (MPa)	Weibull's modulus
Almax	1130	3.0	A1	875	3.0
Altex	1840	4.8	A4	1400	3.0
M 40 B	2800	6.6	C4	2464	6.2
M 40 B	2800	6.6	C5	2567	5.0
M 40 B + Cp	3365	4.9	C6	3139	4.6
M40B+Cp+SiC	3062	5.4	C7	2679	4.2

Then, Altex alumina-silica fiber was chosen in order to get better properties. Castings A3 and A4 gave tensile results which are in accordance with ROM as soon as the residual strength of the leached fibers is used.

Castings A 5 and A6, using Altex fiber with A-357 and A-356 produced composites with a very low longitudinal tensile strength and an increase of transverse strength. Microscopic analysis revealed numerous second phase silicon precipitates in the inter-fiber region. Those brittle bridges between the fibers seem to have a large influence on the longitudinal mechanical properties of the composites. But, on the transverse properties, the increase could be in relation with a chemical reaction between magnesium and silica. This reaction could also reduce the tensile properties of the fiber. However, no difference was observed between a 0.6%Mg alloy and a 0.3%Mg alloy. In order to distinguish the two phenomena, further investigations such as single fiber tensile tests and castings with pure alumina fibers should be performed.

Castings C1, C2 and C3, using M40J carbon fiber with addition of magnesium to pure aluminium in order to reduce melt and preform temperatures showed a reduction of the precipitation of brittle interfacial carbides Al₄C₃, and an increase of longitudinal properties.

Castings C4 and C5, with the less reactive M40B carbon fiber and Al 4.5%Mg at different temperatures demonstrated the direct relation between the time of contact between the molten metal and the fiber, and the longitudinal tensile strength of the composites. Microscopic analysis showed that when the cooling rate decreased, the occurrence of aluminium carbide at the interface increased markedly. Following this observation, the fiber was supposed to be degraded by this reaction, but single fiber tensile tests (Table 3) showed a residual tensile strength of the fiber of 2 464 Mpa in the worse material.

So Weibull statistics on extracted filaments showed that the loss of composite properties due to carbide formation is not in direct relation with a loss of reinforcement properties, but mainly explained by the strong contact between a brittle phase (carbide) and the fiber. SEM fractography of tensile fracture surface of composite from casting C4 are presented in Figure 4. The fracture is a planar fracture with no fiber pull-out which indicates a high interfacial strength.

This was confirmed with the analysis of casting C6. The pyrolytic carbon coating did not eliminate the formation of carbide but this brittle phase was not any more in strong contact with the fiber. Tensile test on single fibers presented in Table 3 confirmed the high residual strength of the fiber. The crack created in the defects (carbide) did not produce a planar fracture surface

of the composite. As shown in Figure 5, the interface delaminated and a pull-out mechanism occurred.

Figure 4. Tensile fracture surface of M40B reinforced Al 4.5%Mg Casting C4, UTS = 350 MPa

Figure 5. Tensile fracture surface of M40B +Cp reinforced Al 4.5%Mg Casting C6, UTS = 1108 MPa

The results obtained on casting C7 showed that the fiber was a little damaged by the several handling steps process (Table 3), and that the tensile strength of the composite is controlled by the shear strength of the pyrolytic carbon layer. Consequently, the properties obtained with this casting were not much higher than those got in casting C6 (Table 2).

In order to avoid the use of expensive coatings, several plates were cast using the graphite fiber FT 700, which is less reactive than the PAN precursor carbon fibers.

Castings C8 and C9 with pure aluminium, confirmed that a decrease of preform and molten metal temperatures has a beneficial effect on the tensile strength of the composite, due to the reduction of carbide formation at the interface.

Using alloys in castings C10 and C11, it was possible to decrease again the processing temperatures, but no benefit was got on the longitudinal properties of composites, and the transverse strength was very low.

Microscopic analysis revealed a heterogeneous distribution of the fibers in the composite, due to the poor wettability of the fibers by the liquid alloys at these temperatures.

On casting C11, numerous second phase silicon precipitates were noticed in the inter-fiber region. But, with this graphite fiber, these brittle bridges between the fibers seem not to have a large influence on the longitudinal mechanical properties of the composites. This is mainly due to the weak interface obtained with this fiber/matrix couple.

So, weak interfaces were obtained on carbon/aluminium composites using a coating of pyrolytic carbon on carbon fibers, or graphite ultra high modulus fibers which are less reactive. A high longitudinal tensile strength was obtained using weak interfaces as compared with stronger interfaces (chemical reaction), even when the matrix contained brittle phases such as carbides or silicon. Conversely, the transverse tensile strength was higher for the stronger interface carbon/aluminium composites. But a compromise has to be found in order to get a low reactivity and an acceptable wettability of carbon fibers by liquid aluminium.

CONCLUSIONS

The first aim was to determine the influence of processing parameters on mechanical properties of composites. The study of non-reactive fiber-matrix systems using pure aluminium and

alumina fibers showed that an increase of metal and preform temperatures has an effect on the transverse strength of composites due to an improvement of the wettability of fibers by liquid metal and consequently, less defects in the material. But a compromise has to be found in order to get a low reactivity and an acceptable wettability when using carbon/aluminium couples.

The second goal was to determine the influence of fiber-matrix reactions on mechanical properties of composites. Castings using carbon fibers with addition of magnesium to pure aluminium in order to reduce melt and preform temperatures showed a reduction of the precipitation of brittle interfacial carbides Al₄C₃, and an increase of longitudinal properties.

The last objective was to study the relation between fiber-matrix interface strength and mechanical properties of composites. A strong interface was obtained with alumina/aluminium couples. When the matrix contained brittle phases like second phase silicon precipitates in the inter-fiber region, the longitudinal mechanical properties of the composites were very low. The carbon/aluminium couples presented the same phenomenon when brittle interfacial carbides Al₄C₃ appeared. A pyrolytic carbon coating on the carbon fiber did not eliminate the formation of carbide but this brittle phase was not any more in strong contact with the fiber. Then, the crack created in the carbide did not produce a planar fracture surface, the interface delaminated and a pull-out mechanism occurred, giving high longitudinal properties to the composite. It was confirmed with a graphite fiber/A-357 alloy casting : numerous second phase silicon precipitates were noticed in the inter-fiber region, but these brittle bridges between the fibers seem not to have a large influence on the longitudinal mechanical properties of the composite due to the weak interface obtained with this fiber/matrix couple.

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